

A panchromatic view of N2CLS GOODS-N: the evolution of the dust cosmic density since $z \sim 7$

S. Berta^{1*}, G. Lagache², A. Beelen², R. Adam³, P. Ade⁴, H. Ajeddig⁵, S. Amarantidis⁶, P. André⁵, H. Aussel⁵, A. Benoît⁷, M. Bethermin⁸, L.-J. Bing⁹, A. Bongiovanni⁶, J. Bounmy¹⁰, O. Bourrion¹⁰, M. Calvo⁷, A. Catalano¹⁰, D. Chéroutrier¹⁰, L. Ciesla², M. De Petris¹¹, F.-X. Désert¹², S. Doyle⁴, E. F. C. Driessen¹, G. Ejlali¹³, D. Elbaz⁵, A. Ferragamo^{11,14}, A. Gomez¹⁵, J. Goupy⁷, C. Hanser¹⁰, S. Katsioli^{16,17}, F. Kéruzoré¹⁸, C. Kramer¹, B. Ladjelate⁶, S. Leclercq¹, J.-F. Lestrade¹⁹, J. F. Macías-Pérez¹⁰, S. C. Madden⁵, A. Maury^{20,21,5}, F. Mayet¹⁰, H. Messias^{22,23}, A. Monfardini⁷, A. Moyer-Anin¹⁰, M. Muñoz-Echeverría²⁴, I. Myserlis⁶, R. Neri¹, A. Paliwal¹¹, L. Perotto¹⁰, G. Pisano¹¹, N. Ponthieu¹², V. Revéret⁵, A. J. Rigby²⁵, A. Ritacco^{26,27}, H. Roussel²⁸, F. Ruppin²⁹, M. Sánchez-Portal⁶, S. Savorgnano¹⁰, K. Schuster¹, A. Sievers⁶, C. Tucker⁴, M.-Y. Xiao³⁰, and R. Zylka¹

(Affiliations can be found after the references)

Received 5 November 2024 / Accepted 27 February 2025

ABSTRACT

To understand early star formation, it is essential to determine the dust mass budget of high-redshift galaxies. Sub-millimeter rest-frame emission, dominated by cold dust, is an unbiased tracer of dust mass. The New IRAM KID Arrays 2 (NIKA2) conducted a deep blank field survey at 1.2 and 2.0 mm in the GOODS-N field as part of the NIKA2 Cosmological Legacy Survey (N2CLS), detecting 65 sources with $\text{SNR} \geq 4.2$. Thanks to a dedicated interferometric program with NOEMA and other high-angular resolution data, we identify the multi-wavelength counterparts of these sources and resolve them into 71 individual galaxies. We build detailed spectral energy distributions (SEDs) and assign a redshift to 68 of them, over the range $0.6 < z < 7.2$. We fit these SEDs using modified black body and Draine & Li (2007) models, and the panchromatic approaches MAGPHYS, CIGALE, and SED3FIT, thus deriving their dust mass (M_{dust}), infrared luminosity (L_{IR}), and stellar mass (M_{\star}). Eight galaxies require an AGN-torus component and other six require an unextinguished young stellar population. A significant fraction of our galaxies are classified as starbursts based on their position on the M_{\star} versus star formation rate (SFR) plane or their depletion timescales. We compute the dust mass function in three redshift bins ($1.6 < z \leq 2.4$, $2.4 < z \leq 4.2$ and $4.2 < z \leq 7.2$) and determine the Schechter function that best describes it. In combination with literature results, we observe an increase of the dust cosmic density, ρ_{dust} , by at least an order of magnitude from $z \sim 7$ to $z \sim 1.5$, consistent with theoretical predictions. At lower redshift the evolution flattens; significant differences exist between results obtained with different selections and methods. The superb GOODS-N dataset enabled a systematic investigation into the dust properties of distant galaxies. N2CLS holds promise for combining these deep field findings with the wide COSMOS field into a self-consistent analysis of dust in galaxies both near and far.

Key words. Galaxies: evolution – Galaxies: mass function – Galaxies: statistics – Galaxies: high-redshift – Submillimeter: galaxies – Dust

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* e-mail: berta@iram.fr

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- ¹ Institut de Radioastronomie Millimétrique (IRAM), 300 rue de la Piscine, 38400 Saint-Martin-d'Hères, France
 - ² Aix Marseille Univ, CNRS, CNES, LAM (Laboratoire d'Astrophysique de Marseille), Marseille, France
 - ³ Université Côte d'Azur, Observatoire de la Côte d'Azur, CNRS, Laboratoire Lagrange, France
 - ⁴ School of Physics and Astronomy, Cardiff University, Queen's Buildings, The Parade, Cardiff, CF24 3AA, UK
 - ⁵ Université Paris-Saclay, Université Paris Cité, CEA, CNRS, AIM, 91191, Gif-sur-Yvette, France
 - ⁶ Institut de Radioastronomie Millimétrique (IRAM), Avenida Divina Pastora 7, Local 20, E-18012, Granada, Spain
 - ⁷ Institut Néel, CNRS, Université Grenoble Alpes, France
 - ⁸ Université de Strasbourg, CNRS, Observatoire astronomique de Strasbourg, UMR 7550, 67000 Strasbourg, France
 - ⁹ Astronomy Centre, Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Sussex, Brighton BN1 9QH
 - ¹⁰ Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, Grenoble INP, LPSC-IN2P3, 53, avenue des Martyrs, 38000 Grenoble, France
 - ¹¹ Dipartimento di Fisica, Sapienza Università di Roma, Piazzale Aldo Moro 5, I-00185 Roma, Italy
 - ¹² Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, IPAG, 38000 Grenoble, France
 - ¹³ Institute for Research in Fundamental Sciences (IPM), School of Astronomy, Tehran, Iran
 - ¹⁴ Physics Department "Ettore Pancini", Università degli studi di Napoli "Federico II", Via Cintia 21, I-80126 Napoli, Italy
 - ¹⁵ Centro de Astrobiología (CSIC-INTA), Torrejón de Ardoz, 28850 Madrid, Spain
 - ¹⁶ National Observatory of Athens, Institute for Astronomy, Astrophysics, Space Applications and Remote Sensing, Ioannou Metaxa and Vasileos Pavlou GR-15236, Athens, Greece
 - ¹⁷ Department of Astrophysics, Astronomy & Mechanics, Faculty of Physics, University of Athens, Panepistimiopolis, GR-15784 Zografos, Athens, Greece
 - ¹⁸ High Energy Physics Division, Argonne National Laboratory, 9700 South Cass Avenue, Lemont, IL 60439, USA
 - ¹⁹ LERMA, Observatoire de Paris, PSL Research University, CNRS, Sorbonne Université, UPMC, 75014 Paris, France
 - ²⁰ Institute of Space Sciences (ICE), CSIC, Campus UAB, Carrer de Can Magrans s/n, E-08193 Barcelona, Spain
 - ²¹ ICREA, Pg. Lluís Companys 23, Barcelona, Spain
 - ²² Joint ALMA Observatory, Alonso de Córdova 3107, Vitacura 763-0355, Santiago, Chile
 - ²³ European Southern Observatory, Alonso de Córdova 3107, Vitacura, Casilla 19001, Santiago de Chile, Chile
 - ²⁴ IRAP, CNRS, Université de Toulouse, CNES, UT3-UPS, (Toulouse), France
 - ²⁵ School of Physics and Astronomy, University of Leeds, Leeds LS2 9JT, UK
 - ²⁶ Dipartimento di Fisica, Università di Roma "Tor Vergata", Via della Ricerca Scientifica 1, I-00133 Roma, Italy
 - ²⁷ Laboratoire de Physique de l'École Normale Supérieure, ENS, PSL Research University, CNRS, Sorbonne Université, Université de Paris, 75005 Paris, France
 - ²⁸ Institut d'Astrophysique de Paris, CNRS (UMR7095), 98 bis boulevard Arago, 75014 Paris, France
 - ²⁹ University of Lyon, UCB Lyon 1, CNRS/IN2P3, IP2I, 69622 Villeurbanne, France
 - ³⁰ Department of Astronomy, University of Geneva, Chemin Pegasi 51, 1290 Versoix, Switzerland

Fig. E.1. N2GN individual sources: multi-wavelength postage stamps and SED fitting results. *Postage stamps:* the bands from left to right and top to bottom are: HST F606W, F814W, F105W, F125W, F160W, CFHT Ks, *Spitzer* 3.6 μm , 4.5 μm , 5.8 μm , 8.0 μm , 24 μm , *Herschel* 160 μm , 250 μm , 350 μm , 500 μm , SCUBA2 850 μm , and NIKA2 1.2 mm, 2.0 mm. The identifications appear with squares of different colors: green for SMA, red for VLA, purple for NOEMA/PDBI and yellow for identification by hand. In addition: VLA sources are marked with gray crosses, SMA sources with gray stars, NOEMA sources with gray X. The chosen counterparts at all wavelengths are marked with circles: blue for SCUBA 850 μm ; orange for SCUBA 450 μm ; red for IRAC, MIPS 24 μm & PACS; cyan for CFHT Ks; pink for Barro et al. (2019); cyan for SPIRE (Liu et al. 2018); red for SPIRE (Elbaz et al. 2011). *Middle panels:* far-IR SED fitting, obtained with DL07 (blue dotted lines), optically-thin MBB (green long-dashed lines) and MBB in general form (red short-dashed lines) models. The light-blue solid lines in the radio domain represent a synchrotron power law linked to the FIR emission by the radio-FIR correlation, in the derivations by Magnelli et al. (2015, upper line) and Delhaize et al. (2017, lower line). *Right-hand panels:* best fit model obtained with MAGPHYS or SED3FIT (high- z versions). The blue dotted lines represent the stellar un-absorbed emission and the orange dashed lines the extinguished model. In case an AGN-torus component is needed (SED3FIT), it is depicted with the dark green long-dashed lines. In few cases where a UV excess is observed but there are no hints for an AGN, we used a young SSP (10 to 100 Myr, bright green long-dashed line) instead of the torus model. The red solid line represents the sum of all components, when needed.

Fig. E.1. continued.

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